

Effects of P and Fe Concentrations in the Medium on the Uptake and Distribution of Fe in Maize Plants (*Zea Mays* L.)

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The subject of the study is the influence of P and Fe concentrations in a nutrient solution on the translocation of Fe. With high P concentrations in the nutrient solution, Fe translocation is affected at all Fe levels, while with high Fe concentrations translocation is also affected when P concentrations are low.

IN many cases, an inadequate amount of Fe is the result of Fe acting on other nutrients and *vice versa*. P is one of the macro-nutrients that take part in this interaction.

The phosphate ion may affect Fe nutrition either through a precipitate mechanism before it is absorbed by the plants¹ or through an inactivating process within the plant^{2,3}.

The present study concerns the effect of P and Fe concentrations in the nutrient solution.

Experimental

For the indoor experiment, a hybrid maize (*Zea Mays* L., H 209) was cultivated hydroponically. "Absorption through the air" was the method used, which is the same as Van Dried's.

The nutrient solution contained varying P and Fe concentrations, while the remaining nutrients remained unchanged⁴.

The experiment factorially combined 4 P levels (1, 10, 100 and 1000 μM) with 3 Fe levels (10, 20 and 40 μM).

The plants were analysed in their phenological state corresponding to pollination and the amount of Fe in the root, stalks and leaves was established through spectrophotometry on the principle of atomic absorption.

Results and Discussion

The Fe concentration in the roots (Fig. 1) shows a tendency towards minimal Fe absorption in more developed plants. This was already observed in barley⁵. It is as if highest yield was coupled with greater Fe mobility or a lesser need for this element. However, other plants, such as beans, act differently, i.e. the Fe concentration is higher in the roots that are more developed⁶.

While there is a tendency towards a lower Fe concentration in the root, it was also observed at the same time that the P concentration in the nutrient solution increased to maximum yield (100 μM P)⁷.

With the same P level in the nutrient solution, the Fe concentration in the root shows a tendency

Fig. 1. Effect of P and Fe concentrations in the nutritive solutions on the Fe levels in the roots, stalks and leaves of maize plants.

to increase when the Fe level in the solution is increased. This is logical and occurs with all P levels that were studied.

What happens in the root also happens in the stalks except that the amount of Fe in the stalks does not increase with the Fe concentration in the nutrient solution for adequate or higher P concentrations (100 and 1000 μM).

With regard to the leaves, the observations made with the root and stalks do not apply. It appears as if Fe in the leaves act more independently compared to the Fe in the nutrient solution.

With the highest Fe level (40 μM), Fe concentration in the leaves decreases when the P concentration in the nutrient solution is increased, the same as in the root and stalks. However, in the leaves, this process continues even after reaching the best yield levels. We believe that translocation in the leaves is more important than absorption as such. This explains the general tendency for Fe to decrease while P increases in the solution, the latter making mobility more difficult for the former.

The effect of a decreased Fe concentration in the leaves after an increase of the P level in the nutrient solution was observed in blueberry plants⁸.

A bibliographic survey of the subject shows, however, that hybrid maize plants Y_{S1}/Y_{S1} , which were treated with a nutrient substance containing a high level of P presented lower Fe concentrations in the root when the P concentration in the nutrient solution was increased. This appears contradictory, at first, to what we observed. A lower Fe concentration is observed in the part of the plant that remains surrounded by air, an observation that coincides with ours. The apparent contradiction, referred to above, may be the result of a saline effect in the nutrient solution since the Fe concentration with which the maize plants are treated (100 μM Fe) is higher than the one used by us (10, 20 and 40 μM Fe)⁹.

The relation $[\text{Fe}_{\text{in tops}}] / [\text{Fe}_{\text{in roots}}]$ (Fig. 2) shows that there are no differences in the lower Fe level (10 μM) in plants treated with a nutrient solution where the P concentration was between 1 and 100 μM . However, a decrease is observed with high P concentrations (1000 μM) and the ratio for normal and higher Fe levels (20 and 40 μM) is optimal with a P concentration of 100 μM , while a decrease occurs both with higher and lower concentrations. This leads to the fact that for low Fe concentrations, Fe translocation suffers mainly with high P concentrations, while with high and normal Fe concentrations in the nutrient solution translocation suffers both with high and low P concentrations. This confirms the existence of an optimal P/Fe ratio, especially with regard to Fe mobility in the plant.

With high P levels in the nutrient solution, maize plants develop symptoms of chlorosis. This may be due to an increasing amount of P in the tissue which produces a greater amount of Fe combined with phosphate. As a result, there is a smaller amount of Fe that can be assimilated

Fig. 2. Relationships between $\text{Fe}_{\text{tops}}/\text{Fe}_{\text{roots}}$ and P in nutrient solutions for each level of Fe in the medium.

through the functions of the nutrient inside the plant, such as the chlorophyll-producing function⁹. Since the Fe combined with phosphore-proteins in the plant cells is ferric and not ferrous, the reason for the P/Fe ratio may be a measure to ensure ferric-ferrous balance in the cells¹⁰.

Through a study of autoradiograms, it was observed that high P concentrations in the nutrient solution made Fe absorption and translocation impossible since the plants resisted interveinal translocation, perhaps because Fe was inactivated or precipitated in the veins and translocation of mesophyll did not take place¹¹.

In conclusion, it may be said that Fe translocation in the maize plant depends on the P concentration in the nutrient solution when the Fe concentration in the solution is high. In all the other cases, only high P concentrations in the solution have an effect on Fe.

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